

Ethics Control Mechanisms and Performance of Water Projects in Tanzania

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Abstract:

The study establishes the influence of ethics control mechanisms on the performance of water projects in Tanzania. The study adopted a critical empirical review of published researches. Specifically, the paper examined the unethical practices in water projects, the common causes for unethical practices and offer possible solutions to mitigate the practices. The end result of the paper is seeing improved implementation of water projects in the country i.e. on time, on budget and of high quality water projects. Findings from reviewed studies revealed that “Dark contracts”, intentional misreporting, inflated contract sum, unfair and dishonest conducts by contractors, fraud, buy-in tactics, bribery and corruption, collusion tendering, taking shortcuts, using substandard materials and shoddy construction significantly affects implementation of water projects in Tanzania. The effects of unethical practices on performance of water projects ranges from over-pricing of activities, time and cost-overruns, delays in water projects implementation, low absorption of resources and finally poor quality of water projects. Therefore, the opposite of the above, is that projects that went through due processes are highly correlated to their performance and sustainability. From my review, projects of this category seem to be limited given the ethical dilemma in the country. These findings indicate non-compliance to Public Procurement Act (2011) by contractors in public projects for many years. The paper concludes that if government control’s ethics, performance of water projects would be obvious. Contractors and consultants would have insignificant influence if the government is upright there and complies with the legal requirements not based on recommendation from third party. This paper forms a foundation and feedback to the

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water sector in Tanzania. It recommends transparency and publication of contracts, use of whistleblowing-channels, strengthening project management control systems, client involvement and strict contract exit strategy based on Post Implementation Review report to ensure successful performance of water projects in Tanzania.

Keywords: Ethics, control mechanisms, performance, water projects, Tanzania,

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INTRODUCTION

The question of project ethics is viewed by project managers from different angles. When making ethical judgments, some are merely bound by legal requirements, contracts, society's norms and the professional code of ethics. Project ethics control is a critical issue of any organization, including an industry, a company or government as unethical practices often affect the performance and image of an organization.

Public sector projects have an inherited tendency, where majority are rarely implemented lucratively in African countries. The projects that were funded by the Government of Tanzania (GoT) together with donor partners have demonstrated poor performance, which is a key source of disappointment to project stakeholders as well as beneficiaries. Despite this experience, these tendencies continue to be the rule in the contemporary reality. In 2010 World Bank projects failure rate was 39% and unsuccessful projects by the same bank was over 50% in Africa (Ika, 2009).

Project ethics which are made up of several values influence the behaviors of project team in the workplace. Although they vary in different organization, ethics and values are usually adopted by entire organization and its projects and used to complete all tasks. Contingent on this, Alfred (2008) as cited by Rahman, 2014 assert that ethics refers to an overall system comprising of moral principles that are used in determining whether individual attitudes and actions are right or wrong. In other words, ethics are the norms, moral principles and attitudes of what could be considered by the community as appropriate or inappropriate and are used in controlling different profession practices.

Rahman, 2014 citing Arnoudov study of 2012, indicates that ethics impact work implementation. Almost all organizations provide individuals with their work ethics. This is often in form of working manual that is aimed at making the working process for employees, including new recruits easier as it contains ethical directions, rules, in addition to norms and value systems associated with the organization.

Victor and Cullen (1957) as cited by Rahman, 2014, assert that project performance can be improved if an organization adopts an ethical culture. This happens when ethics is demonstrated by the management and spread to all employees occupying different levels.

Project management is considered as an important field given the impacts of projects to the socio-economic development of our lives and the nation. Projects transform the future of

individuals as well as the country (Bredillet, 2014). Project tasks, dilemma and environment are controlled, shaped and managed by project managers who by nature are humans.

Project managers make decisions based on their professional together with industrial standards of practice, and the provided regulations. They also manage pluralistic or conflicting interests presented by various stakeholders and demonstrate their commitment towards delivering exceptional outcome. Ethical decisions are crucial to any business environment such as organizations and the society due to their notable implications. Project managers who are ethical, competent as well as experienced are always considered as important drivers for not only successful projects implementation, but also organizations.

The increased unethical behaviors in projects in developing countries has led to the drop in quality of projects as evidenced by statistics collected from different construction sites. For this issue to be prevented, several strategies need to be implemented to improve organizational ethics along with projects performance. Simply put, this study focuses on revealing unethical practices in water projects, their causes and finally proposes the possible mitigation strategies.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Water problem in Tanzania is acute as more than 60% of Tanzanians both in rural and urban areas lack access to clean and safe water (World Bank, 2018). The implementation of water projects in the country over the past decades has been affected by many challenges. The government of Tanzania, the World Bank, and other development partners play a key role in water projects support and their resources cannot be wasted without implementing appropriate measures to the sector.

Making accurate project management decisions depend on accurate information received and processed by the project team. Project problems arise when the project managers together with other decision makers willingly fail to disclose negative project news. Reluctance in acting on negative project news often results in unfavorable project delivery not only in terms of processes, but also end results. Misinformed decision makers in projects are likely to feeble and may lead to costly and embarrassing collapse of projects. Controlling all project aspects deem important to enhance performance of projects.

In project settings, misreporting of the actual project status either unintentionally or intentionally and finding excuses and convincing yourself that is not bad is dishonesty. Bredillet (2014) supports this view by indicating that unethical behavior by an organization significantly affects the outcome of projects negatively.

Experiences from previous implemented water projects in Tanzania indicate that large national programs can be challenging to manage and their quality are difficult to ensure, especially during the initial years of implementation. According to World Bank (2018) report, in 2016 more than 40% of water points in Tanzania were non-functional, with many failing in their first to three years after construction. The results revealed that excessive focus on new construction and installation of water systems that the local communities do not have the capacity to manage limit water points' sustainability.

TAWASANET (2019) surveyed 83,000 water points in Tanzania and found that 60 percent of the failures in their first to three years were a result of managerial problems attributed to unethical practices, wrong pump type selection, and weak feasibility studies to establish water table. Project managers also went for unspecified technologies and materials contrary to the requirements of projects. The National Audit Office report reveals that more than 65 water projects implemented by 22 LGAs valued at TZS 63.7 billion were delayed for completion for a period ranging from 3 to 48 months in 2018. The delay was due to incompetent contractors, bureaucracy, inadequate release of funds by the Government, design challenges and procurement weaknesses (NAO, 2018). Likewise, on September 2019, the GoT declared a total of 88 major water projects dating back to 2010 as stalled. Among the issues raised for stalled projects include, poor management and unscrupulous engineers. This is an indication of severe malpractices in the public procurement process.

On 25 September 2019, the Government of Tanzania suspended issuance of permits to contractors implementing water projects countrywide due to unrealistic project cost estimations. A newly formed authority, with less than a-year experience, the Rural Water Supply and Sanitation Agency (RUWASA) and the country's water and sanitation authorities to be in charge of all water projects. Theoretically, this could be the worst decision ever, as water projects will be affected severely by bureaucracy and corruption tendencies inherited in these authorities hence time delays and cost overruns.

On this note, numerous methodologies, tools, techniques and guidelines have been developed over many years to facilitate the management of projects and programs. However, many development projects and programs ranging from construction industry, defense, information technology, financial services, in addition to water projects continue to present poor performance as evidenced with their failure to deliver the anticipated benefits. The dynamics associated with public projects, specifically water projects, represent an important gap in

understanding. This study explored the varied performance of these water projects, why some water projects financed by DPs succeeded and why others failed? Whether adopting a mixed approach of project ethics controls mechanism will improve performance of water projects in Tanzania.

Purpose of the Study

- To identify the unethical practices and their consequences on water projects in Tanzania
- To describe the reasons behind unethical practices in Water sector projects in Tanzania
- Suggest the modalities of mitigating unethical practices in water projects in Tanzania.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Literature

The current study is based on the Agency and Institutional theory that was originally developed to specifically describe the association between owners and managers of an organization. Agency theory is widely employed as a governance theory to handle the relationship between principals and agents (Davis, Schoorman, & Donaldson, 1997). Its application in organizations is premised on demonstration of the importance of dividing ownership and controlling tasks through allocating governing roles to the principals and managerial responsibilities to managers who act as agents with self-centeredness, utility-maximization traits besides presenting interaction skills characterized by imbalance of information.

Although agency theory gained popularity from its informative explanation of specific aspects of organizational complexities, its applicability is limited by the strict economic perspective it advocates.

Contingent on the identified limitations of agency theory, Davis et al. (1997, p.20) assert that "Additional theory is needed to explain relationships based on other non-economic assumptions." The current study employs this suggestion as institutional theory will be used in explaining the behaviors of public institutions in Tanzania. According to Henisz, Levitt & Scott (2012), institutional theory focuses on the processes that are established by social structures such as normative and behavioral systems, how they are stabilized, and the changes they undergo with time.

Using the word agent in reference to project manager, sponsor as well as owner, or team, the four ethical principles can be conclusively presented in project management context as: the agents are required to behave appropriately so that their actions can be used as moral standard by others occupying the same position and they should also act in a way that demonstrates significant respect for the interested parties' interests. The agents are also recommended to evaluate the project based on their moral standards and take actions that they can content besides considering the wellness of the majority in the running project when executing their actions.

The theories that have been introduced and discussed are applicable in the current study as project managers (agents) act as representatives of the client (government) in water projects implementation. In most cases the contractor (agent) is well-informed of the project progress as compared to the client (government). As of human nature, the contractor will always try to maximize their own benefits at the expense of his client.

The project activities as well as situations and context are the responsibilities of the project managers since they are the ones that make decisions based on the professional and industry standards as well as contract requirements. Crawford (2005) also notes that project managers utilize regulatory rules together with regulations of a company in managing pluralistic as well as conflicting interests presented by different stakeholders as they aim at delivering the best outcome. Premised on this, it can be concluded that honest and competent project managers play critical role that contribute not only successful projects but also successful organizations.

Empirical Literature

Weaknesses in decentralized system in the country, including lack of institutional support and bureaucratic administrative structures specifically in rural settings has for a long time limited citizen engagement, advocacy, finance mobilization and management of water resources. Hence, many water projects have become nonfunctional after a short period of operation (Henisz, et al., 2012). Worldwide, bureaucracy is used as a tool to mobilize and control people but modern bureaucracies in Tanzania, exhibit nonprofessional structural and procedural in attaining the country's goals, ending up in ineffectiveness and inefficiencies in government operations.

The country not only suffers from financial problems but also unethical practices in government projects and too many regulating bodies which are in conflict with each other.

Their policies and regulations are not in line. Harmonization of government policies and regulations is fundamental to enhance performance of water projects in the country.

Several studies have discussed the ethical aspects of project management. Similarly, Professional Project Management Associations have come up with Codes of Ethical and Professional Conduct. As an illustration, PMI has code of ethics that inform project management practitioners on what is considered right and honorable practice (Helgadottir, 2008). The PMI code of ethics mainly advocates responsibility, respect in addition to fairness and honesty that should be observed by PMI members in the global project management.

“PMI Ethical Decision-Making Framework” presents a five-step process which an individual can employ when addressing an ethical dilemma issue. These steps include: “Assessment, Alternatives, Analysis, Application of ethical principles, and Action.” When applying ethical principles as guided in step 4, an individual is required to ask oneself three primary questions: “(i) would the action lead to the greatest good? (ii) Would the choice treat others the same way the user would like to be treated? (iii) Would it be fair and beneficial to all concerned?” (IPMA, 2015b).

IPMA also deals with ethics in varied contexts based on its recent version of competence baseline that is presented as “IPMA Code of Ethics and Professional Conduct.” Equally, the British Association for Project Management (APM) provides a code of professional conduct outlining the responsibilities of members with ‘honesty,’ ‘respect,’ in addition to other headings.

Despite the existence of varied professional codes, studies indicate that modern project managers execute their responsibilities in complex and turbulent environment, work with stakeholders from varied settings, and they often experience dilemma in making decisions (Ingason, 2015). According to Ingason (2015), project managers also handle many different risks that change with advancement of project life cycle. However, the most critical part of the challenges experienced by project managers is the diverse commitments they have towards project owners together with interested parties. They are often required to prevent conflict of interests from affecting their actions besides respecting the parties’ confidentiality. Project managers have also varied commitments not only to co-workers, but also employees to guarantee them protection of health through observance of safety measures and safe working environment.

Ingason (2015) also acknowledges the responsibility of project managers to the society. He notes that, project managers should ensure their actions are not detrimental to the

communities, societies as well as economies. Mishra et al. (2011), Schieg (2009), Eskerod and Huemann (2013), and Gareis et al. (2013) as cited by Ingason (2015), share a similar view as they indicate that completion of projects should always be considerate of sustaining ethicality in addition to social values.

Business ethics are often associated with ethical dilemmas in addition to ethical judgments (Guy, 1990). They are divided into two; normative together with descriptive ethics (O'Fallon & Butterfield, 2005). Normative ethics are greatly associated with moral philosophy (Ingason, 2015). Descriptive ethics on the other hand focuses on the sphere of management along with decision-making and is mainly interested in explaining and predicting the actual conduct and behaviors of individuals.

Ethical decisions are considered appropriate in business since they result in remarkable implications on business as well as society. Premised on this, ethical decision-making has remained a topic of interest for many years as demonstrated by the works of classical Greek philosophers including Socrates, Plato without the exception of Aristotle which is influential to business study. Today's society is also grappling with questions relating to philosophical questions revolving around morality and ethics (Bredillet, 2014).

Significant interest has been demonstrated by organizations as well as project management towards ethics and ethical issues. In connection with this claim, Tuner & Muller (2005), provide globalization and ethics as excellent examples of issues affecting industries today. Competition is likely to lead to undesirable effects in businesses and projects. Despite this, ethics is uncommon subject in the researches that have been conducted in Tanzania in reference to general management.

The author of this study found Turner and Muller's (2005) study necessary in the current research as it illustrates varied forms of ethical issues affecting organization's governance structures. The three issues found significantly correlate to ethical problems limiting water project performance in Tanzania. These include: 1. transparency issues relating to the manager's reluctance to report actual performance in an organization, 2. relationship issues that involves poor interpersonal as well as informal relationships between stakeholders, including clients, suppliers, and staff with managers, 3. optimal issues that focus on optimization to realize the objectives of clients, sponsors as well as managers of specific projects in addition to distraction associated with risks and benefits from the identified stakeholders.

Currently, traditional supply chains are made up of numerous-tiered supplier networks such as contractors but with the absence of a link between suppliers and client. According to Kulmala et al. (2002), use of many-tiered supplier results in increase of transaction cost before it reaches the final client who carries the burden of cost. Costs associated with many-tiered supply costs together with traditional supply chain costs increases significantly the cost of project implementation (Kulmala et al., 2002).

Being ethical is a human character and should apply in water projects in Tanzania. However, there are numerous negative human influences including the cost of management systems, manipulation and performance measurements. Transparency International (2013), note that, most people use any available resources to promote a bad job so as to complete it with the intention of making profit. There are some contractors that use a lot of their effort in generating profit from varied claims instead of improved construction methods.

Practice of unbalanced bid is also a common behavior in contractors that results in cash constraints on the involved parties like complications of cash flow to the contractors and financial disorder to associated parties including clients when managing over one project (Kulmala et al., 2002). Although the accusation is premised squarely on the contractors, it is imperative to note that the client's behavior also can influence negative project outcomes. For instance, delayed payments by clients often encourage contractors to use short-cuts due to cash constraints.

Many projects in Tanzania are hardly completed within time, budgeted resources and as per specifications. The factors behind this undesired performance mostly are within the capacity of those in charge of the projects. Poor quality constructions, wrong infrastructure and inflated work prices all results from governance failures.

On measuring water project performance, this study settled on three parameters which include time, cost as well as quality which are variables used in evaluating client's satisfaction as guided by the arguments presented by different studies. These parameters are also employed in the monitoring, evaluation as well as controlling a project. Despite the existence of many parameters, studies appear to focus on schedule and cost as they impact project performance significantly.

As it was established before, project ethics is an important facet for successful outcome of projects. It guides the decision making of the owner when the right information is presented to them. Likewise, project managers should use realistic cost estimates in running their cost management for effective implementation of projects. Thus, budgeting together with cost

control is imperative to successful completion of projects but they are usually marred with challenges when projects are run by dishonest personnel.

Varied practices of project management have been identified through researches and experiences and are documented in literature. However, little is documented about the role played by project ethics control on performance of projects. Based on this, it was a recommendable to conduct a research to establish methods that are effective in controlling ethics for water projects.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The paper is a theoretical essay. Empirical data collection approaches included a comprehensive review of the underlying theories and empirical researches on project ethics guided by key words globally and later narrowed to Tanzania. Informal discussions with construction professionals and observations based on the experience of the writer were also useful to reach the conclusion.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

From the reviewed empirical researches on unethical practices on the performance of Tanzania's water projects, some common unethical practices, causes, and their control mechanisms were identified (Table 1).

Table 1: Common unethical practices, causes and control mechanisms

Unethical practices in projects	Common causes	Ethics control mechanisms
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Intentional Misreporting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Balancing costs through lowering the functionality of the project • Hope of recovering via varied means at some time in the future • Protect reputation • Fear of termination of project • Fear of losing bonus or other incentives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Openness and communication • Building transparency culture • Code of Ethics

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fear of face-loss by associated with admitting planning mistakes • Covering for team members 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Inflated Contract sum ▪ Wired bids and Contracts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kickbacks • Dishonesty • Retired government officers as agents of bidding contractors (networks). • Profit motive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regular publication of contracts and implementation details (Government: websites, Journals and Newspapers) • Strengthening institutions and anti-corruption agencies • Display boards (amount and duration) • Whistleblowing Channels • Code of Ethics
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Negligence and shoddy construction ▪ Incomplete projects ▪ Using substandard materials ▪ Compromising on the participants' safety ▪ Violating the established standards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shortcuts (to meet deadlines or budgets) • Lack of client oversight to monitor performance • Inexperienced contractors/Manager 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regular M&E • Proper exit strategy • Employee ethics awareness • Competent and experienced contractors • Clear policies as well as procedures for the projects
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Unfair and dishonesty conduct ▪ Fraud 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of leadership by example • Self-centered interest 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employees training on ethics • Ethics rewarding system • Whistleblowing channels • Code of Ethics • Ethics focused-governance
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Dark contracts ▪ Buy-in (Bidding low to force contract changes in future) ▪ Bribery and Corruption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weak law enforcing institutions • Greed • Impunity culture 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transparency in contracting and implementation • Upholding and enforcing the rule of law • Strengthening PPRA • Good Leaders

Public construction projects in Tanzania spend a significant percentage of overall government expenditure where a large part is on procurement of resources. Ideally, an efficient public procurement system determines the quality of infrastructure developed. Therefore water projects development and an efficient public procurement cannot be separated.

The following are the other general unethical practices as revealed by NAO (2018a, 2018b, 2018c, 2018d & 2019) reports as were reported from many Local Government Authorities (LGAs) and other public entities across all public projects in Tanzania other than in table 1; an awareness of them could help project teams improve project implementation.

Commencement of procurement proceedings without sufficient funds; Payments for non-existing goods/services (*RAHCO made advance payment of USD 500,000 equivalent to TZS 1.07 billion to Advisor STG South Africa for consulting services of Standard Gauge Railway in 2015. However, the service was not provided to the company till the time of the audit in February 2019*); Use of single source and restricted tendering instead of competitive procurement method; goods and services procured/payment made without records; Irregular and unsupported contracts; Contracts awarded to non-substantially responsive bidder; Unauthorized spending (*unapproved TPB's Procurements TZS 247 Million*).

Failure by Evaluation Committees to declare conflict of interests is another unethical practice; Irregular disqualification of the lowest evaluated bidder leading to a loss; Procurement made without Tender Board Approval (*TZS 2,747,729,852.51*); Contract signed with unregistered joint venture/company; Goods and services procured from unapproved suppliers; Goods paid for but not delivered and Goods received but not inspected; Inconsistence of tender requirements provided in tender documents (advertisement and the submitted bids); Change of a contract's start date without proper authorization.

Also deliberate and unauthorized variations beyond the scope of the contract is a common unethical practice in public projects (*Tanzania Bureau of Standards-TBS- procurements, the NAO report 2018 noted that in executing contract PA/044/2017-18/HQ/W/03 for Construction of Sample receiving block, Fence and Guard's House TZS 498.26 million were spent over and above the approved TZS 162 million, thus, making overspending of TZS 336.26 million without proper authority*); Deviation from BOQ during contract implementation; Tender not advertised in a widely circulated newspapers; Projects not reflected in the quarterly procurement report; Unjustifiable reasons for Re-tendering and Disqualification of tender without concrete reasons (*TANESCO awarded tender to M/s Agro Vision Limited under a contract No. PA/001/2016-*

17/HQ/G/01 for supply of Handheld X-ray Spectrometer at the cost of TZS 1.89 billion, however, M/s. Infratech Limited was a qualified bidder at a bid price of TZS 1.33 billion).

The above unethical practices lead to offences of financial misconduct like public officers acting in unauthorized power, incurring wasteful spending, and disregarding the call for provision of financial information as required by relevant Acts. Other financial misconduct includes failure of the management to keep the right records, possessing public funds illegally, misappropriation of funds as well as assets, concealing information relating to public finances with the intention of gaining financial benefit; and practicing corruption in form of soliciting as well as receiving an inducement.

DISCUSSION

Delays in water projects implementation

Ethic control mechanisms should facilitate public entities together with their vendors to efficiently provide required services to the public. Unfortunately, public inefficiencies such as design challenges, destruction of water system and disasters, procurement weaknesses, ineffective COWSO, incompetent contractors, bureaucracy and inadequate release of fund by the Government have led to delayed implementation of many projects. These findings are in line with NAO (2018) report, which revealed that, about 65 water projects implemented by 22 Local Government Authorities amounting TZS 63,720,208,963.97 were delayed for completion for a period ranging from 3 months to 48 months.

Low absorption of resources

Unethical practices in public projects have contributed to poor assimilation of the development budget. Project resources are not spent for the intended purposes, which in turn has led to often re-allocation of money on same projects. Money is spent on travel, study tour, vacation, seating allowances, meetings and endless feasibility studies. This is confirmed in the NAO (2018) report which indicates that improvement in the general performance in a state's budget implementation did not impact the absorption rates for what is referred to as development expenditures positively as they remain low. For instance, the report (table 9-50) notes slow progress on implementation of water projects worth TZS 3,356,170,900.

Over-pricing of activities

Most public water projects are characterized by over pricing, through contracts, collusion bidding as well as buy-in tactics, contrary to their value for money. Some LGAs experienced incomplete projects despite full budgeted amount disbursement. Such projects lead to

increased public spending and loss of public revenue. The Auditor General report (2018) indicates that Magamba Village is yet to be connected to the water project due to shortage of pipe lines which were initially underestimated at 1,200 meters long while the actual requirement is 14,000 meters long for the same budget. Furthermore, in Nyang'hwale District Council, six water projects were delayed to be completed due to cost overruns.

Cost and Time-overrun

Unethical practices like bribery and corruption, incompetent contractors and “buy-in” which refer to bidding low with the intention of making corners or forcing successive contract changes have led to cost overruns and delayed water projects implementation. A good example is the New Sola Water Filter Project: The objective of the project was to construct a filter valve at a cost of TZS 3,500,000,000 to purify water in Zanzui dam in Misungwi, Simiyu Region where at least 11 villages were expected to be covered by the project and it had started earlier August 2015 and its completion date was estimated to be 31, March, 2017. Unfortunately, the contractors (Petty-Co-Operation Ltd and Josam Company Ltd) failed to deliver the project on time. The Minister for Water and Irrigation, Mr. George Lwenge, had to intervene and give the companies an extension of not more than 132 days to complete the project, otherwise legal measures could be taken against the contractors.

Inferior quality of Water projects

Studies in water projects indicate that many water points failed in their first to three years of implementation (World Bank, 2018 & NAO, 2018). The cited reasons include use of marginal (substandard) materials, incompetent contractors, managerial problems, wrong choice of pump type, unfair and dishonest conducts of contractors, fraud, manipulation of performance measurements and inappropriate feasibility studies.

A good number of Water projects in Tanzania are of poor quality despite extensive investment. Kalabezo Water Project in Buchosya-Sengerema where more than TZS 1,490,000,000 has been spent at shoddy work and the NG'APA Water Project (Lindi)-more than TZS 21,800,000,000 out of TZS 29 billion had been paid but not of expected functionality. The project had delayed for more than two years. On March, 3rd, 2017, President, Dr. John Pombe Magufuli had to step in and ordered to put on hold the contractors' passports (Mr. Rajendra Kumar and his assistants) of Overseas Infrastructure Alliance Ltd. The Bunda Water project from Lake Victoria is another poor quality water project in Lake Zone Tanzania.

Recommendations

To ensure performance of water projects in the public sector in Tanzania the study recommends: transparency and publication of contracts and implantation details is key (openness and communication); Water and Sanitation Authorities should strengthen their oversight to monitor performance. This should include management of not only control systems, result controls, and action controls, but also personnel controls in addition to cultural to influence behaviour on performance. Routine-based control is recommended.

Strengthening the Anti-Corruption Agency (PCCB) and the Public Procurement Regulatory Authority (PPRA) and reviewing the public tendering process to reduce bureaucracy and ensure timely take off of projects. To grantee performance in water projects the study recommends the use of Contracts with strict Exit strategy based on a Post-Implantation Review (PIR) report.

The study considers it appropriate for project management teams to promote stakeholder participation to guarantee water project beneficiaries satisfaction, sense of ownership and future sustainability. It also recommends project staff to always to consider their work ethics and also be motivated by ethics-focused reward system such as bonuses on their salaries.

Scope of Further Research

Attaining project management triangle parameters (time, cost and quality) in public sector projects remain a big challenge. Academicians and Researchers could do more work on whether Integrating Army Discipline in public projects execution could improve their performance.

Conclusions

The current study establishes a literature review base for addressing ethics control mechanisms on performance of water projects in Tanzania. From the findings, it is now clear that unethical practices in water projects affect the country's economic development and the social welfare of the communities.

One may conclude that unethical practices are common in public projects. Major unethical practices identified include inflated contracts (wired bids and contracts), followed by bribery and corruption in tendering, then unfair and dishonesty conducts by contractors (fraud) and lastly, negligence and shoddy construction.

It is interesting to note that the reasons behind these unethical practices include self-centered interest, weak law-enforcing institutions, covering for team members and their organisations,

lack of client stringent oversight, lack of transparency in public contracts, use of inexperienced contractors and project managers and finally the desire for shortcuts.

In this paper, various effects of unethical practices on performance of water projects as perceived by eminent researchers were identified as over-pricing of activities, time and cost-overruns, delays in water projects implementation, low absorption of resources and finally inferior quality of water projects.

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